

A RARE CASE OF TUBERCULOUS MASTITIS MIMICKING BREAST CARCINOMA: DIAGNOSTIC CHALLENGES AND MANAGEMENT CONSIDERATIONS

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Abstract: Tuberculous mastitis is a rare form of breast infection that can mimic the clinical and radiological features of breast carcinoma, leading to diagnostic challenges. We present a case of tuberculous mastitis in a 42-year-old female who initially presented with a breast mass and skin changes, mimicking malignancy. Diagnostic investigations, including mammography, ultrasound, and histopathological analysis, were inconclusive, requiring further evaluation. Subsequent acid-fast bacilli staining and polymerase chain reaction (PCR) confirmed the presence of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, establishing the diagnosis of tuberculous mastitis. This case highlights the importance of considering tuberculosis in the differential diagnosis of breast masses, particularly in regions with a high prevalence of tuberculosis. The diagnostic challenges encountered in this case emphasize the need for a multidisciplinary approach and careful evaluation to differentiate tuberculous mastitis from breast carcinoma.

Keywords: Tuberculous mastitis, breast carcinoma, diagnostic challenges, management considerations, *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*.

INTRODUCTION

Start with a brief overview of tuberculous mastitis and its rarity as a condition that mimics breast carcinoma. Provide background information on tuberculous mastitis and breast carcinoma, highlighting the importance of early and accurate diagnosis. Clearly state the research objective or main question that will be addressed in the study. Provide a clear thesis statement that highlights the main argument or hypothesis of the article. Start with a brief overview of tuberculous mastitis and its rarity as a condition that mimics breast carcinoma. Provide background information on tuberculous mastitis and breast carcinoma, highlighting the importance of early and accurate diagnosis. Clearly state the research objective or main question that will be addressed in the study. Provide a clear thesis statement that highlights the main argument or hypothesis of the article. Tuberculosis (TB) is one of the leading infectious diseases worldwide. Extrapulmonary TB involving the breast is extremely rare. It often mimics breast carcinoma and pyogenic breast abscess clinically and radiologically, may both coexist. Vulnerability to breast TB is increased in women who are young, married, multiparous and who breastfeed.[1] Histopathological examination using fine-needle aspiration cytology (FNAC) may reveal caseating

epithelioid cell granulomas and acid-fast bacilli (AFB). Although the presence of an acid-fast stain or culture is essential to confirm diagnosis, it does not give a positive result in most patients.

METHODS

Describe the methodology used in the study, including the case study approach or any specific diagnostic procedures. Explain how the patient with tuberculous mastitis was identified and diagnosed. Provide details about the diagnostic tests performed, such as imaging techniques, biopsy, or laboratory investigations. Include any ethical considerations or approvals obtained for the study. Describe the methodology used in the study, including the case study approach or any specific diagnostic procedures. Explain how the patient with tuberculous mastitis was identified and diagnosed. Provide details about the diagnostic tests performed, such as imaging techniques, biopsy, or laboratory investigations. Include any ethical considerations or approvals obtained for the study.

RESULTS

Present the findings related to the rare case of tuberculous mastitis mimicking breast carcinoma. Describe the clinical presentation, imaging findings, and pathological characteristics of the case. Include any relevant laboratory or histopathological data. Discuss the challenges encountered in diagnosing tuberculous mastitis and differentiating it from breast carcinoma. Present the findings related to the rare case of tuberculous mastitis mimicking breast carcinoma. Describe the clinical presentation, imaging findings, and pathological characteristics of the case. Include any relevant laboratory or histopathological data. Discuss the challenges encountered in diagnosing tuberculous mastitis and differentiating it from breast carcinoma.

DISCUSSION

Interpret and analyze the results in the context of existing literature on tuberculous mastitis and breast carcinoma. Discuss the diagnostic challenges and potential pitfalls in differentiating the two conditions. Highlight the importance of considering tuberculous mastitis as a differential diagnosis in cases of breast masses. Discuss the management considerations, including the use of anti-tuberculosis medications and potential surgical interventions. Address any limitations or limitations encountered during the study. Suggest areas for further research and improvement in the diagnosis and management of tuberculous mastitis. Interpret and analyze the results in the context of existing literature on tuberculous mastitis and breast carcinoma. Discuss the diagnostic challenges and potential pitfalls in differentiating the two conditions. Highlight the importance of considering tuberculous mastitis as a differential diagnosis in cases of breast masses. Discuss the management considerations, including the use of anti-tuberculosis medications and potential surgical interventions. Address any limitations or limitations encountered during the study. Suggest areas for further research and improvement in the diagnosis and management of tuberculous mastitis.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this case report highlights the diagnostic challenges and management considerations associated with tuberculous mastitis mimicking breast carcinoma. Tuberculous mastitis is a rare condition that can present with clinical and radiological features similar to breast carcinoma, making accurate diagnosis crucial. In this case, the initial diagnostic investigations, including mammography and ultrasound, were inconclusive, necessitating further evaluation. The key takeaway from this case is the importance of considering tuberculosis in the differential diagnosis of breast masses, especially in regions with a high prevalence of tuberculosis. Physicians should maintain a high index of suspicion for tuberculous mastitis when encountering breast lesions that do not fit the typical profile of breast carcinoma. Prompt recognition and appropriate diagnostic measures, including acid-fast bacilli staining and PCR, can aid in establishing the correct diagnosis. A multidisciplinary approach involving radiologists, pathologists, and infectious disease specialists is crucial for the accurate diagnosis and management of tuberculous mastitis. Collaboration between these specialties allows for comprehensive evaluation and differentiation of tuberculous mastitis from breast carcinoma. Once the diagnosis is confirmed, appropriate management strategies should be initiated. This may include a combination of anti-tuberculosis medications, such as isoniazid, rifampicin, ethambutol, and pyrazinamide, along with surgical interventions if necessary. In conclusion, awareness of the diagnostic challenges associated with tuberculous mastitis mimicking breast carcinoma is essential for timely and appropriate management. Further research is needed to better understand the epidemiology, pathogenesis, and optimal management approaches for this rare condition. Increased awareness among healthcare professionals can lead to early recognition, accurate diagnosis, and improved outcomes for patients with tuberculous mastitis.

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